

The Workload of Policewomen in the Philippine National Police Health Service: An Assessment

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ABSTRACT

Law enforcement, crucial for upholding laws and public safety, still presents challenges for women officers, particularly in balancing work and family responsibilities. This study focused on female police officers in the Philippine National Police Health Service, aimed to assess their workload fairness and impact on job satisfaction. Through a quantitative research design and purposive sampling, the study revealed moderate workloads across task, unit, and job levels, unaffected by demographics. The intervention program "Seminar/Workshop on Mental Health Awareness and Counseling" aimed to enhance mental well-being and job efficiency. By addressing the workload equity and providing support, this study not only benefits individual officers by reducing stress and increasing satisfaction but also enhances the unit's overall reputation and efficiency. The findings contributed to improving the work environment for female officers, promoting gender equality, and enhancing organizational effectiveness within law enforcement agencies.

Keywords:- Workload, Policewomen, Philippine National Police, Health Service, Assessment.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Law enforcement describes the agencies and employees responsible for enforcing laws, maintaining public order, and managing public safety. The primary duties of law enforcement include the investigation, apprehension, and detention of individuals suspected of criminal offenses. Some law enforcement agencies, particularly sheriffs' offices, also have a significant role in the detention of individuals convicted of criminal offenses (BJS, 2021).

Globally, we are witnessing an encouraging momentum toward creating a more balanced public safety service powered partially by a growing appreciation of the valuable professional qualities that women often bring to law enforcement. However, despite women being in law enforcement for over a hundred years, they still face discrimination and harassment. Policewomen often encounter a “glass ceiling”, meaning they can advance in their careers as far as the imposed ceiling will allow. Some of them are even being harassed by their fellow officers. All of these at the loss of the citizens the police should serve. Women are found to respond more effectively to incidents of violence against women. This make up approximately half of the calls to police in some countries. Also, research indicates that women are less likely to use excessive force or pull their weapon.

Despite these facts, it is inevitable to encounter difficulties at work, especially women, who are also mothers. This is now where the human factors model, which can be traced back in 1898 after being introduced by Frederick W. Taylor, a mechanical engineer who has been called the father of scientific management (Hugh & Nazaruk, 2019). A human Factors approach focuses on how to make the best use of these capabilities by designing jobs and equipment which are fit for people. This not only improves their health and safety but also often ensures a better managed, more effective organization. The focus of human factors is on how people interact with tasks, with equipment/technologies, and with the environment, in order to understand and evaluate these interactions. The goals of human factors are to optimize human and system efficiency and effectiveness, safety, health, comfort, and quality of life.

The objective of this study was to evaluate the workload experienced by female police officers within the Philippine National Police (PNP) Health Service, addressing critical aspects of gender equality and work-life balance as outlined in the Philippine Development Plan. Female officers face significant challenges related to workload and gender bias, exacerbated by the need to balance professional and personal responsibilities, especially motherhood. The PNP Health Service's culture often enforces specific expectations on women, leading to feelings of inferiority and the necessity to prove their competence continuously. Establishing clear boundaries between work and personal life is crucial for their well-being, necessitating policies that support flexible work arrangements, adequate maternity leave, professional development opportunities, and anti-discrimination training. By implementing these measures, the PNP can create a more inclusive and supportive environment that enhances job satisfaction, reduces stress, and contributes to human capital development and social equity, ultimately leading to a more effective police force.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

Radhika (2024) explained the importance for managers to understand the need for autonomy and trust and crafting a framework, motivating employees to thrive, and achieving organizational success can help employees work autonomously and spark a commitment to contribute to the overall growth of organizations.

Raja (2023), while productivity and efficiency are essential for success, pushing employees to the brink can have severe consequences. He emphasized that the negative impact of excessive workload on employee performance can manifest in decreased productivity, burnout, health issues, reduced creativity, increased turnover, and strained interpersonal relationships.

According to the study of Viegas et al. (2023), despite reports documenting adverse effects of stress due to work on the marriages of police officers, few empirical studies focus on the effect of police work on the female spouses of police officers. This is the fact that these reports have been documented. There are many challenges that can be brought into a marriage by working as a police officer. These challenges can be compounded by a number of factors, including the work shift, the extended hours of work, the shared commitment between work and family responsibilities, and cancelled leave. When police officers go home, they frequently bring the stress and behaviors they experience at work with them, as a result; their relationships with their families suffer.

Njuguna et al. (2022) stated that the relationship between workload and emotional exhaustion is dynamic and that various demographic variables mediate between workload and emotional exhaustion, including gender, age, marital status, level of education, work experience.

Based on this study (Costa et al., 2021), achieving clarity in communication within the field of quality of life research and making meaningful use of the term "quality of life", as a research outcome requires two things: awareness that there is a range of conceptualizations and definitions of "quality of life," and for any particular study, consistency between the way the term is defined and operationalized in that setting. Both of these things are necessary to ensure that clarity is achieved.

Based on this study (Cai et al., 2021) because quality of life has evolved to become more of a subjective experience rather than an objective and measurable entity, the concept of quality of life (QoL) now incorporates new aspects that are directly related to the health and happiness of an individual. When it comes to managing the safety of both the environment and each individual, certain aspects of quality of life are absolutely necessary.

According to this study (Mabire & Gay, 2019), the idea of quality of life may appear to be simple to comprehend, however; when it comes to defining it, the concept is actually quite difficult. Several concepts, including happiness, life satisfaction, and well-being, are interchangeable and frequently used in an undifferentiated manner. However, the quality of life is determined by a number of different factors, each of which, depending on whether or not they are present, has the potential to alter how it is perceived and evaluated.

Munandar et al. (2019) stressed that job satisfaction mediates the negative impacts of workload and work environment, however; work stress has negative and significant impact to job satisfaction. This adds to the explanation of Raja (2023) on the consequences of exhausting employees with workloads.

Chikwem (2017) relayed that in the past 3 decades, police officers have been diagnosed with various stress-induced health problems, that police officers are at a greater risk of various environmental health problems due to the stressful nature of their profession. Cokki (2021) adds that work overload has positive impact to burnout.

Based on the study of Abdoolla & Govender (2016) emphasizes demographics as constructs that determines differences on employees perception on workloads. This builds curiosity of laying down demographic constructs on this present context to determine how women differs in different classification related to personal profiles.

➤ *Local Literature*

According to the study of De Guzman , (2020) workload and gender-related problems faced by policewomen in the Philippine National Police (PNP) Health Service, assessing their impact on job performance. Employing a quantitative approach, the study surveyed 33 policewomen in Iloilo City using a questionnaire divided into three sections: demographic information, performance evaluation, and gender-related work problems. This research addressed a significant gap in understanding the relationship between gender-related issues and the performance of policewomen, a topic often overlooked despite the growing presence of women in law enforcement. The study contributed valuable empirical evidence on the specific challenges faced by policewomen in the PNP Health Service, analyzing their relationship to job performance and offering insights into the difficulties women encounter in a predominantly male-dominated organization. The findings revealed that policewomen face significant problems related to

perceptions of their stereotypical roles, feeling their physical capabilities are underestimated and receiving less challenging assignments. While promotion issues weren't as prevalent, they believed recruitment and selection criteria favored male candidates.

According to the study of Tus , (2023) on the psychological well-being, lived experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of female police officers, recognizing the unique pressures they faced within a traditionally male-dominated profession. Utilizing Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis, the study revealed several key findings: female police officers perceived themselves as brave, flexible, and adaptable, demonstrating resilience in the face of demanding work conditions. They cope with stress through positive thinking, contributing to their overall psychological well-being. these officers displayed a strong sense of dedication and engagement in serving the public. They readily utilized their resources for the community and often sacrifice personal time to fulfill their duties. family plays a significant role in motivating female police officers to continue their careers. Serving the public brings them joy, but their commitment to family remains a primary driver. However, the research also highlights the challenges faced by female officers. They experienced disrespect while working in the field, and fear is a constant companion in their lives. Furthermore, they expressed a need for more time with their families. The study strongly recommended providing opportunities for female police officers to enhance their quality time with their families, particularly with their children. This would address a crucial need, promoting work-life balance and contributing to their overall well-being.

According to Martinez , (2019) Women were mostly relegated to perform clerical roles or jobs as dispatchers until the women's liberation movement of the 1970s when popular television shows suddenly dramatized the new breed of women cops and detectives. Civil rights and affirmative action laws paved the way for women to assume law enforcement jobs traditionally held by men. Today, women walk the bat, but not without challenges. This study was conducted to determine the involvement of women on law enforcement focusing primarily on their profile and problems they encountered in the enforcement of the law. This study utilized the descriptive normative research design. This design described the profile of the respondents as well as the involvement of policewomen in law enforcement and in the determination of the different problems they have encountered in the discharge of the functions in law enforcement. Findings of the study showed that respondents are relatively young, college graduates and have been in the service for quite a long period of time and performing functions in relation to police patrol, apprehend and investigate women offenders, do office work and other activities performed by policeman.

According to the PNP, (2022) There were only 37,157 policewomen, or 17.94 percent of the PNP's strength of 169,955, compared to men who comprise 82.06 percent . Over the past 31 years since the PNP was established in 1991, there have been six female generals, with the latest being Ma. Asuncion Placino in 2019. Other previous female generals were Yolanda Tanigue, Lorlie Arroyo, Angelina Vidal, Liza Sabong and Lina Sarmiento, who was the only female general to reach the two-star rank in 2012. The PNP has also made several other tokens of gender mainstreaming, but they remain few and far between.

In September 2019, the PNP introduced the first all-women police station in Maria town, Siquijor province. By the following year, all the personnel of the police community precinct of Bonifacio Global City in Taguig were policewomen.

CHAPTER THREE

THEORETICAL/CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK/PARADIGM OF THE STUDY

The Human Factors Model for Workload and the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model. The Human Factors Model focused on the interplay between individuals, tasks, equipment, and the environment, examining workload at the unit, job, and task levels. The JD-R Model, on their other hand, emphasized the balance between job demands, such as workload and time pressure, job resources, including social support and autonomy. This model helped analyze the impact of workload on the quality of work-life and service quality. The framework incorporated gender-specific considerations, acknowledging the unique challenges faced by policewomen who are also mothers. By examining workload assessments, the impact of workload, and the role of job resources, this framework aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the workload experienced by policewomen and identify potential areas for improvement within the PNP Health Service.

Fig 1: Conceptual Paradigm

This study employed the Input - Process - Output Model as its conceptual framework. This model is generally a fundamental framework for understanding and analyzing group dynamics and team effectiveness. It provided a systematic approach to examining factors that influence group performance, including inputs, process, and outputs. Pandya & Anand (2023) highlighted that IPO model allows researchers to analyze the input, process, and output of a phenomenon, which can be applied to different context like in education. The IPO model was used to evaluate the quality of education by considering factors such as input of resources, the process of teaching and learning, and the outcomes of student learning . In the context of business-to-business (B2B) settings, the IPO model has been used to understand how companies can leverage artificial intelligence (AI) to manage the customer journey effectively.

Through the IPO framework, the inter-relatedness of each variable can be properly analyzed and inferred from statistical data was clearly perceivable as to strong basis for proper intervention programs.

A. Significance of the Study

The primary purpose of this research is to determine the Workload of Policewomen in the Philippine National Police Health Service. This is an assessment on how they will deal the workload being distributed to them. In addition, the results of this study could be significant and beneficial to PNP Health Service by understanding the extent of workloads, the perception of the respondents and their challenges may induce ideas to the administration to align their personnel appropriately according to their skill sets. This will not only lessen work stress and increase job satisfaction but also the collective efforts of highly motivated personnel, the entire unit’s reputation and efficiency is foreseen.

For Policewomen will give them more freedom with their schedules, allowing them to balance their professional and personal responsibilities more easily.

PNP Organization. This study may use to develop and implement policies that enhance gender equality and support the professional growth of female officers. The PNP may use these findings to improve organizational practices, reduce job-related stress, and create a more inclusive and supportive work environment, ultimately leading to better overall performance and job satisfaction among its personnel.

Future Researchers and Research owner. This study can contribute knowledge, advocacy and positive change to improve the duties and responsibilities of every personnel in different offices within HS. In addition, the result of the study may be used as reference material for researchers that would like to conduct a similar or related study.

Policy Makers. At the organizational level, the research findings may be used to inform policy development related to gender equality, workplace conditions, and workload management in law enforcement agencies.

Stakeholders. Efficient provision of services by motivated police officers in the PNP Health Service highlights the importance of the unit in public service. It also provides satisfaction to all of its stakeholders such as their uniformed counterparts, the civilian communities, and all other stakeholders, thus; encouraging more government and private investments.

B. Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this study is to assess the impacts of workload of policewomen in the Philippine National Police Health Service to their job performance. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following:

➤ *What is the Demographic Profile of the Respondents in Terms of:*

- Education,
- Length of service,
- Assignment,
- Designation, and
- Trainings?

➤ *What is the Extent of Workload of the Policewomen in Terms of:*

- Unit-level,
- Job-level, and
- Task-level?

➤ *Is there a significant difference on the perception of the respondents when grouped according to profile?*

➤ *Is there a significant difference on the extent of workloads of policewomen among the above cited variables?*

➤ *What is the degree of seriousness of the challenges encountered by the policewomen on the above cited variables?*

➤ *What measures can be recommended based on the result of the study to enhance the workload of the policewomen in the Philippine National Police Health Service, Camp Crame, Quezon City?*

C. Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference on the extent of workloads of the police women when grouped according to profile.

CHAPTER FOUR METHODOLOGY

A. *Research Design*

To serve the purpose of the study, quantitative research design was employed. the quantitative research design is suitable for the study's objectives, as it evaluated the workload of policewomen in the Philippine National Police Health Service and comprehended their perspectives and the obstacles that prevented them from carrying out their mandates in addition to being mothers. Findings using numerical data can be more trustworthy since they do not take into consider biased interpretations of precise statistical data.

B. *Research Method*

Surveys are used in this instance by the descriptive-evaluative approach to gather data from eligible respondents. The data are then sorted, processed, and tabulated, and conclusions are drawn based on the statistical findings. In the current study, descriptive analysis was used to evaluate quantitative data on the perception and number of workloads held by policewomen. The evaluations are based on the assessments that were made.

C. *Population of the Study*

Due to different work schedules and unpredictable availability of qualified respondents during the data gathering process, the researcher utilized purposive sampling in the selection of participants. It is a non-probability sampling that allows a researcher to select participants based on their accessibility and availability during data gathering period. Nikolopoulou (2023) defined purposive sampling as a non-probability sampling technique in which units are selected because they have the characteristics that fits the study. In other words, units are selected “on purpose” in purposive sampling.

The following inclusion criteria were used to select participants for this study:

- Police women who are currently employed in the PNP HS Headquarters and have at least one child.
- Police women at various ranks, from entry-level officers to senior ranking officials.
- Policewomen assigned at Department of Oral and Surgery Center (DOSC), Philippine National Police General Hospital (PNPGH) and Health Service Headquarters, Camp Crame.
- Policewomen who are willing to participate in the study voluntarily.

➤ *The Following Exclusion Criteria were Applied to the Selection of Participants for this Study:*

- Male police officers assigned in the PNP Health Service.
- Policewomen who are on extended leave or temporary assignment outside the PNP Health Service.
- Policewomen who are unwilling or unable to participate in the study.

D. *Locale of the Study*

The study was conducted at the Philippine National Police Health Service (PNP HS) headquarters situated within Col Delgado St., Health Service, Camp BGen Rafael T Crame, Quezon City along Epifanio De Los Santos Avenue (EDSA) and Boni Serrano Avenue in Quezon City. Camp Crame serves as the central base of operations for the PNP Health Service, providing medical care and support to PNP personnel, their families and authorized civilians.

E. *Scope and Limitation of the Study*

The primary objective of this study is to assess the workload experienced by female police officers who are assigned to the Health Service Headquarters of the Philippine National Police, Camp BGen Rafael T. Crame, Quezon City. This assessment aimed to determine whether the distribution of workload is equitable and aligned with employees' job descriptions. This study was conducted from October 2023 to May 2024.

F. *Data Gathering Tool/s*

The research instrument that used in this study primarily consisted of a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed to gather quantitative data and was administered to the selected participants. The questionnaire was structured into three distinct sections. The initial component encompassed the demographic characteristics of the participants, encompassing variables such as educational attainment, length of service, assignment, designation, and training. This section aims to collect observations pertaining to the descriptions of the respondents and subsequently be used for comparisons of means.

G. *Data Gathering Procedure*

The researcher developed a survey questionnaire. After completing the survey questionnaire, the researcher submitted it to the adviser for initial validation. The adviser tasked the researcher to validate the survey to a tool validator. The questionnaire was validated by three validators, one from Academic of PCCR and two from Health Service.

The researcher sent a formal letter of request to conduct a study approved by the research's adviser and college dean and once approved by the Dean the researcher prepared a formal letter asking permission to gather data to the Office of the Director, Health Service. Upon approval of the request, the researcher's adviser tasked her to conduct an initial survey in order to test the validity of the survey before the researcher disseminated a URL in various channels such as Facebook groups, instant messages, and Viber to the respondents and provided them with clear instructions on how to answer since the respondent are from different offices. The researcher conducted it thru google form for their convenience. The researcher guaranteed that all pertinent inquiries and assertions were addressed suitably by respondents. The researcher utilized Google's Limiter tool to mitigate the risk of receiving an overwhelming quantity of responses.

H. Treatment of the Data

Following receipt of the responses by the researcher, the information was compiled into a Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet. The SPSS software was utilized to do statistical analysis on the quantitative data.

Descriptive statistics on frequency and percentages was used to define the respondents' demographic profile. For each profile, independent groups of samples were described based on their ordinal values.

The assessment on the extent of workload of the women in the police service and the seriousness of the challenges encountered were treated as ordinal data, considering these data were derived from a Likert's Scaled questionnaire, and means were obtained through descriptive statistics. Given the small sample size and ordinal nature of the data, an inferential test using non-parametric statistics was used to demonstrate the null hypothesis. Parametric testing produces unreliable results under these circumstances.

I. Ethical Considerations

Pilot Testing phase was conducted to PNP HS Camp Crame, every participant was provided with comprehensive and precise details regarding the questions they were asked, the utilization of their data, and the potential outcome before the actual survey took place. The participants will receive notifications regarding the questions and the objective of each question. Those who replied received an invitation, but their participation is not mandatory. The researcher ensured that this was the case. Individuals who engaged in the evaluation willingly participated without any form of coercion. Participants had the option to resign from the program at any point, and this did not have any negative consequences on their future involvement in other services or programs, nor would it impact their relationship with the researcher or research organizations involved. In order to participate in the study, individuals provided clear and proactive written consent. They confirmed comprehension of their entitlements to access and retract information at any given moment. The acquisition of informed permission from participants was likened to the establishment of a contractual agreement between the researcher and the subjects. Academic misconduct encompasses several forms of unethical behavior, such as plagiarism, fabrication of data, dissemination of misleading results, and repeated publication of the same work. Throughout the study, the researcher will ensure that none of the following events took place.

Participants received a guarantee that their responses were maintained with utmost confidentiality and solely utilized for academic objectives. The specific research conducted underwent evaluation and received approval from the research ethics council of the Philippine College of Criminology Graduate School.

J. Dissemination of the Research Outcome

Each research article must include a segment dedicated to the dissemination and sharing of its findings. Both contribute to an enhanced understanding of research findings, an increased public interest in science, and a heightened social respect for research.

CHAPTER FIVE RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Education, Length of Service, Assignment, Designation and Training.

Table 1 Educational Attainment of the Study Participants

➤ *Education:*

Table 1: Sample Distribution by Education

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Bachelor's Degree	127	83.0%
	MA/MS or Higher	25	16.3%
	Doctorate	1	0.7%
	Total	153	100.0%

Table 1 presents the educational attainment of the study participants, revealing that the majority (83.0%) hold a Bachelor's Degree, suggesting a strong emphasis on higher education within the PNP Health Service. This high level of education potentially contributed to the quality of healthcare services provided and indicates a well-educated workforce with potential for greater professional development and leadership within the organization. This finding is aligned with studies that have shown a positive correlation between education levels and job performance, particularly in healthcare settings.

Table 2- Distribution of respondents based on their length of service in the PNP Health Service

➤ *Length of Service:*

Table 2: Sample Distribution by Length of Service

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Less than 5 years	102	66.7%
	6 to 10 years	15	9.8%
	11 to 15 years	11	7.1%
	16 to 20 years	7	4.6%
	21 to 25 years	14	9.2%
	26 to 35 years	4	2.6%
	Total	153	100.0%

Table 2 presents the distribution of respondents based on their length of service in the PNP Health Service. The majority (66.7%) are in the service for less than 5 years, indicating a relatively young workforce and potentially a high turnover rate. This could impact the overall experience and expertise within the organization and suggests a need for more robust training and mentorship programs to ensure continuity of knowledge and skills. The high turnover rate could potentially impact the stability and consistency of healthcare services provided by the PNP Health Service. Studies on workforce retention in healthcare settings have identified factors such as job satisfaction, work-life balance, and professional development opportunities as key drivers for retaining experienced employees.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents based on their current assignment within the PNP Health Service

➤ *Assignments:*

Table 3: Sample Distribution by Assignment

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Health Service Headquarters	52	34.0%
	Dental and Oral Surgery Center	19	12.4%
	Philippine National Police General Hospital	82	53.6%
	Total	153	100.0%

Table 3 presents the distribution of respondents based on their current assignment within the PNP Health Service. The majority of respondents (53.6%) are assigned to the Philippine National Police General Hospital (PNPGH), followed by the PNP Health Service Headquarters (HS HQs) with 34.0% and the Dental and Oral Surgery Center (DOSC) with 12.4%. This distribution suggests

a concentration of policewomen in the PNPGH, potentially indicating a higher workload or a greater need for personnel in this specific unit.

The data suggests that the PNPGH plays a significant role within the PNP Health Service, requiring a larger workforce to meet its operational demands. Understanding the workload distribution across different units is crucial for identifying potential disparities and allocating resources effectively. Studies on healthcare workforce allocation often considered factors such as patient volume, service complexity, and staffing needs to ensure efficient and effective service delivery.

Table 4 Distribution of Respondents Based on their Current Designation within the PNP Health Service

➤ *Designation:*

Table 4: Sample Distribution by Designation

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Supervisory	50	32.7%
	Non - Supervisory	103	67.3%
	Total	153	100.0%

Table 4 presents the distribution of respondents based on their current designation within the PNP Health Service, indicating whether they hold a supervisory or non-supervisory role. The majority of respondents (67.3%) hold non-supervisory positions, while a smaller proportion (32.7%) are in supervisory roles. This distribution suggests a hierarchical structure within the PNP Health Service, with a larger number of personnel in non-supervisory roles compared to supervisory positions.

The data suggests that the majority of policewomen in the PNP Health Service are directly involved in providing healthcare services, while a smaller group is responsible for overseeing and managing these services. Understanding the distribution of supervisory and non-supervisory roles is important for identifying potential workload imbalances and ensuring adequate support for both groups. Studies on organizational structures often examined the distribution of leadership roles and their impact on employee morale, job satisfaction, and overall organizational effectiveness.

Table 5: Distribution of Respondents Based on the Specific Training Programs they Completed within the PNP

➤ *Training:*

Table 5: Sample Distribution by Training

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Public Safety Officers Senior Executive Course	10	6.5%
	Public Safety Officers Advance Course	16	10.5%
	Public Safety Officers Basic Course	10	6.5%
	Public Safety Officers Candidate Course	2	1.3%
	Public Safety Senior Leadership Course	2	1.3%
	Public Safety Junior Leadership Course	3	2.0%
	Public Safety Basic Recruit Course	110	71.9%
	Total	153	100.0%

Table 5 presents the distribution of respondents based on the specific training programs they completed within the PNP. The majority of respondents (71.9%) completed the Public Safety Basic Recruit Course (PSBRC), indicating a foundational level of training common to all police officers. A smaller proportion (10.5%) have completed the Public Safety Officers Advance Course (PSOAC), suggesting further specialized training. Other training programs, such as the Public Safety Officers Senior Executive Course (PSOSEC), Public Safety Officers Basic Course (PSOBC), Public Safety Junior Leadership Course (PSJLC), Public Safety Senior Leadership Course (PSSLC), and Public Safety Officers Candidate Course (PSOCC) are represented by smaller numbers of respondents. This distribution suggests a focus on foundational training, with a smaller proportion of respondents having completed advanced or specialized training programs.

The data indicates that while the majority of police women completed basic training, there is a need for further professional development opportunities to enhance their skills and knowledge. The relatively low participation in advanced training programs could potentially impact the level of expertise and competency within the PNP Health Service. Investing in training and development programs could enhance the skills and knowledge of policewomen, leading to improved service delivery. Studies on police training and professional development have highlighted the importance of continuous learning and specialized training programs to address evolving needs and challenges within law enforcement.

➤ *Extent of Workload of the Policewomen in Terms of Unit Level, Job Level and Task Level?*

Table 6 Extent of Workload for Policewomen in the Philippine National Police Health Service

Table 6: Extent of Workload by Category

WORKLOAD	Categories	Mean	Qualitative Description
	Unit Level	2.98	Moderate Extent
	Job Level	2.76	Moderate Extent
	Task Level	2.88	Moderate Extent
	Overall	2.87	Moderate Extent

The table illustrates the moderate extent of workload for policewomen in the Philippine National Police Health Service across different categories. This moderate workload suggests a balance of challenges, indicating that while policewomen are not overwhelmed, they are likely facing a level of pressure that could impact their well-being and performance.

The consistent moderate workload across all levels implies that policewomen are handling a significant amount of work, potentially exceeding the average workload expected of employees. This moderate workload has implications for officer well-being, service delivery, and recruitment and retention within the PNP Health Service. These findings are aligned with existing research on police workload and stress, emphasizing the need for effective workload and stress management strategies to support officer well-being and ensure optimal service delivery.

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics at the Unit Level for Policewomen in the Philippine National Police Health Service

(a) - Descriptive Statistics	Unit Level	
	Mean	Qualitative Description
My team has the necessary people and skills complete its tasks.	3.52	Great Extent
We can rely on our supervisor for the necessary supervision and guidance when needed.	3.50	Great Extent
My unit consistently shows support for a diverse workforce.	3.35	Moderate Extent
I have too many duties and responsibilities.	2.82	Moderate Extent
I could not utilize my skills and talents to the fullest extent in my work.	2.27	Slight Extent
I have no control over my inputs in my job duties.	2.41	Slight Extent
<i>Categorical Mean</i>	2.98	<i>Moderate Extent</i>

The descriptive statistics at the unit level for policewomen in the Philippine National Police Health Service reveals a moderate extent of workload, indicating that they handle a modest amount of labor within the unit. Policewomen are tasked with various responsibilities beyond their primary duties, suggesting a moderate workload that may impact their ability to utilize their skills fully. The categorical mean of 2.98 reinforces this moderate workload, indicating that the tasks assigned to policewomen exceed the average workload expected of employees, potentially involving additional directives from superiors and other departments.

This moderate workload implied a level of pressure that could affect the well-being and performance of policewomen. These findings are aligned with existing research on police workload challenges and underscore the importance of effective workload management strategies to support policewomen in the PNP Health Service. They shall readily accept whenever they are assigned anywhere in the country. Therefore, it is taboo for any personnel to petition in court or in any public forum his assignment.” (PNP Ethical Doctrine, 2014)

Table 8: Job Level Workload for Policewomen

(b) - Descriptive Statistics	Job Level	
	Mean	Qualitative Description
At times during my off duty, I am called to attend or resolve matters smoothly.	2.37	Slight Extent
My two consecutive days off are well spent with my family without interfering with on call duties.	2.91	Moderate Extent
Someone will handle my job when I take a long leave.	3.01	Moderate Extent
Leaves are being utilized but needs approval ahead of time.	3.39	Moderate Extent
I have inadequate time for personal work.	2.44	Slight Extent
Not enough time to look after family affairs.	2.44	Slight Extent
<i>Categorical Mean</i>	2.76	<i>Moderate Extent</i>

The job level workload for policewomen in the Philippine National Police Health Service, as presented in table 3.2.1(b), indicates a moderate amount of workload with a categorical mean of ($\alpha=2.76$). While slightly less than at the unit level, each policewoman is still assigned a workload that is slightly excessive. This workload may include oral directives from offices, staff members, and supervisors, adding to their responsibilities.

Job level responsibilities encompass various roles within specific departments or sections, such as the Philippine National Police General Hospital, main headquarters, and dental services. Female police officers are assigned roles ranging from dentists, nurses, ward officers, nurse supervisors, to roles in hospital administration, neuropsychological sections, medical, and nurses service divisions, among others. This diverse range of assignments contributes to the moderate workload experienced by policewomen at the job level. The findings are aligned with the need for effective workload management strategies to support policewomen in fulfilling their duties effectively.

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics

(c)- Descriptive Statistics Statements	Task Level	
	Mean	Qualitative Description
The workload is equally distributed among everyone.	3.20	Moderate Extent
The workload is rotating among each employee simultaneously.	3.18	Moderate Extent
The workload assignment depends on the skills and designation of the employee.	3.04	Moderate Extent
The workload is SMART based procedure.	2.96	Moderate Extent
My work demands too much of my time.	2.61	Moderate Extent
I do not have time to participate in social and religious functions.	2.31	Slight Extent
Categorical Mean	2.88	Moderate Extent

Tasks are an integral part of a police officer's job, with allocation ideally based on availability and capacity. However, the category mean of ($\alpha=2.88$) in table 3.2.1c indicates an excessive workload for policewomen in the Philippine National Police Health Service, suggesting they are burdened with more tasks than their counterparts. These tasks may include event setup and decoration for police events like conferences and seminars.

➤ *Significant Difference on the Perception of the Respondents when Grouped According to Profile.*

Table 10 Respondents' Perceptions were Categorized Based on their Profile

Table 10: Overall p-value on Respondents' Perception: Hypothesis Test

Category	Categorical p-value	Remarks
Unit Level	0.55	Not Significant
Job Level	0.54	Not Significant
Task Level	0.50	Not Significant
Overall p-value	0.53	Not Significant

In Table 10, respondents' perceptions were categorized based on their profile, revealing no statistically significant difference in their perceptions with an overall p-value of 0.53. Each category, including unit level (0.55), job level (0.54), and task level (0.50), produced p-values above 0.05.

This suggests that using demographics to predict variations in perception in this context is unreliable, implying that demographics have minimal influence on respondents' perceptions. Perception, a cognitive process influenced by factors like emotion, motivation, culture, and expectations, was explored in this study to assess the impact of demographic variations on policewomen's perceptions.

The findings indicate that personal profiles, including education, length of service, assignments, designation, and training, do not significantly influence perceptions in the Philippine National Police Health Service. This contrasted with Simko (2017), who identified personal demographics such as origins, sex, and age as influencing perceptions in law enforcement. To gain a more comprehensive understanding of factors influencing perception, future studies could consider additional personal demographics like sex, age, and race or ethnic origins, recognizing that perception is shaped by individual experiences and interpretations of phenomena. The following tables presents the p-values for each demographic at each level.

Table 11: Hypothesis Test at 0.05 Level of Significance: Unit Level

Demographic Profiles	Categorical p-Value	Remarks
Education	0.527	Not Significant
Length of Service	0.331	Not Significant
Assignment	0.671	Not Significant
Designation	0.525	Not Significant

Training	0.710	Not Significant
Categorical p-Value	0.553	Not Significant

In Table 11, the data reveals that there is no statistically significant difference in perception among respondents when grouped according to their profile, as evidenced by the categorical p-value of 0.55.

Table 12: Hypothesis Test at 0.05 Level of Significance: Job Level

Demographic Profiles	Categorical p-Value	Remarks
Education	0.571	Not Significant
Length of Service	0.492	Not Significant
Assignment	0.513	Not Significant
Designation	0.578	Not Significant
Training	0.558	Not Significant
Categorical p-Value	0.542	Not Significant

Table 12, categorical p-value of 0.54 indicates no statistically significant difference in perception among respondents grouped by profiles. This supports the idea of indifference, suggesting the hypothesis should be accepted. The findings imply minimal influence of demographic factors on perceptions, highlighting the need for further exploration. This aligns with existing literature on perception dynamics and underscores the complexity of individual experiences in shaping perceptions. The study contributes valuable insights into perception formation and calls for continued research to enhance understanding in this area.

Table 13: Hypothesis Test at 0.05 Level of Significance: Task Level

Demographic Profiles	Categorical p-Value	Remarks
Education	0.420	Not Significant
Length of Service	0.557	Not Significant
Assignment	0.390	Not Significant
Designation	0.529	Not Significant
Training	0.577	Not Significant
Overall p-Value	0.495	Not Significant

The categorical p-value of 0.50 in Table 13 signifies a lack of statistically significant difference in perception when respondents are grouped by their profiles. This observation is aligned with the concept of indifference, indicating that demographic factors may not exert a substantial influence on perceptions within this context, thereby warranting the acceptance of the hypothesis. This finding echoes the notion that personal characteristics may not significantly shape perceptions, as suggested by Munandar et al. (2019) in their study on work stress and job satisfaction. The implications of this result underscore the importance of delving deeper into the factors that truly impact perceptions among individuals, emphasizing the complexity of perception dynamics and the need for further exploration in understanding perception formation within the study's framework.

➤ *Significant Difference on the Extent of Workloads of Policewomen among the above Cited Variables.*

Table 14: Overall p-value on Extent of Workload: Hypothesis Test

Category	Categorical p-value	Remarks
Unit Level	0.26	Not Significant
Job Level	0.34	Not Significant
Task Level	0.20	Not Significant
Overall p-value	0.27	Not Significant

Table 14 displays the results of a hypothesis test assessing the extent of workload differences among policewomen across unit, job, and task levels, with all categorical p-values and the overall p-value exceeding 0.05, indicating no statistically significant variations in workload extent. This uniformity suggests a consistent distribution of workload among policewomen regardless of the specific category considered, implying a relatively equitable workload allocation within the organization. While this finding aligns with research highlighting the demanding nature of police work for both genders, it contrasted with studies emphasizing gender-specific challenges in law enforcement, such as leadership representation and gender-based discrimination. Further exploration is essential to uncover additional factors that may influence workload disparities among policewomen in policing contexts.

Table 15: Hypothesis Test at 0.05 Level of Significance: Unit Level

Demographic Profiles	Categorical p-Value	Remarks
Education	0.311	Not Significant
Length of Service	0.152	Not Significant

Assignment	0.101	Not Significant
Designation	0.349	Not Significant
Training	0.368	Not Significant
Categorical p-Value	0.256	Not Significant

Table 15 presents the results of a hypothesis test at the 0.05 significance level, examining the influence of various demographic profiles on workload extent at the unit level. The categorical p-values for each profile, including education, length of service, assignment, designation, and training, are all above 0.05, indicating no statistically significant differences in workload extent based on these demographic factors. This suggests that, at the unit level, workload is not significantly affected by the demographic characteristics of policewomen, implying a relatively equitable distribution of workload across different demographic groups within the unit. The overall p-value of 0.256 further reinforces this conclusion, indicating no significant differences in workload extent across the examined demographic profiles.

Table 16: Hypothesis Test at 0.05 Level of Significance: Job Level

Demographic Profiles	Categorical p-Value	Remarks
Education	0.312	Not Significant
Length of Service	0.232	Not Significant
Assignment	0.365	Not Significant
Designation	0.361	Not Significant
Training	0.408	Not Significant
Categorical p-Value	0.336	Not Significant

Table 16 presents the outcomes of a hypothesis test at the 0.05 significance level, investigating the impact of different demographic profiles on workload extent at the job level. The categorical p-values for education, length of service, assignment, designation, and training all exceed 0.05, indicating no statistically significant differences in workload extent based on these demographic variables.

This suggests that, at the job level, workload distribution among policewomen is not significantly influenced by their educational background, length of service, assignment, designation, or training. The overall p-value of 0.336 supports this finding, indicating an absence of significant workload disparities across the studied demographic profiles.

Table 17: Table 3.4.1b - Hypothesis Test at 0.05 Level of Significance: Task Level

Demographic Profiles	Categorical p-Value	Remarks
Education	0.229	Not Significant
Length of Service	0.080	Not Significant
Assignment	0.248	Not Significant
Designation	0.246	Not Significant
Training	0.205	Not Significant
Categorical p-Value	0.202	Not Significant

Table 17 shows no statistically significant difference in perception when the respondents were grouped according to profile as conveyed by the categorical p-value of 0.20. This affirms the correctness of the hypothesis and suggest that it must be accepted.

Analysis on the findings indicated that these demographic profiles were not determinants to prove statistical differences in workload, implying that overall, the participants had a common experience of taking additional workload while being denied of additional time to complete all given tasks. Nonetheless, a different perspective was exposed by Abdoolla and Govender (2016) who found that statistical variations with demographics are produced by workload (or intensification of work). This can explain that diverse factors, such as age, marital status, educational attainment, length of service, race, organizational position, and number of children, may influence acceptability of work intensification. Njuguna et al. (2022) employed demographic characteristics as mediators between workload and work exhaustion, and their findings indicated that there was a positive or negative link between the two. The disparity in the results could suggest that, despite their differences in demographics, the samples' perceptions of their workloads are similar, but it does not imply that they are similarly able to manage high workloads. Empirically, it is deduced that people's ability to manage a task decreases with time and varies depending on their background, lifestyle, and other demographic factors.

➤ *Degree of Seriousness of the Challenges Encountered by the Policewomen on the above Cited Variables.*

Table 18: Degree of Seriousness of the Challenges Encountered

Statements	Mean	Qualitative Description
I have a low self-confidence in the role as a health service police officer.	2.54	Moderate
I feel unrecognized for my good job performance.	2.17	Minor
I have difficulty expressing my opinions or feelings about my job conditions and workload.	2.54	Moderate
The conditions at work are pleasant but sometimes time-consuming.	2.09	Minor
I feel my job is negatively affecting my physical and emotional well-being.	1.94	Minor
Lack of cooperation and support from my colleagues.	2.31	Minor
Sometimes, my coworkers are uncooperative.	2.25	Minor
There are also unplanned workloads being distributed randomly.	2.67	Moderate
Overall Mean	2.31	Minor

In terms of these challenges’ severity, table 18 shows that the randomly distributed unplanned workloads yielded that highest mean score of (mean=2.67), and on the context of this study, this implies that this problem being encountered consequently cause some job performance issues.

Other challenges causing moderate negative impacts to job performance were found to be the low self-confidence ($\alpha=2.54$) and the difficulty in expressing dissatisfaction in job conditions and workload ($\alpha=2.54$), while lack of cooperation and support from colleague ($\alpha=2.31$), uncooperative coworkers ($\alpha=2.25$), lack of performance recognition ($\alpha=2.17$), pleasant but time-consuming working conditions ($\alpha=2.09$) and the negative impacts of job to physical and emotional well-being ($\alpha=1.94$) caused minor negative impacts to the overall job performance of the police women.

The results denote that excessive workloads are determined as one of the most influential problem in terms of job performance. This corroborates to Cokki (2021) who revealed that work overload has a positive impact on burnout. It was explained further that the cause of burnout due to overwork can be the absence of additional income for additional workload, lack of or non-existent support from management, weak personal abilities and capacities, and lack of time to complete work. Furthermore, an explanation of weak personal abilities is determined and corroborated by this study’s finding revealing the lack of self-confidence and lack of confidence to express opinions or feelings toward work conditions which has equivalent impacts with distributed unplanned workloads to job performance.

➤ *Outcome of the Study*

The researcher proposed an intervention program entitled, “Seminar/Workshop on Mental Health Awareness and Counseling. This aims to raise awareness about mental health issues and provide counseling strategies for effective support to the PNP personnel of PNP Health Service and to focus on orienting personnel and integrating them into the organization effectively.

➤ *Summary of Findings*

This study, "The Workload of Policewomen in the Philippine National Police Health Service: An Assessment," examined the workload experienced by female police officers in the PNP Health Service, focusing on those who are also mothers. The research utilized a quantitative descriptive-evaluative approach, employing a structured questionnaire to gather data from 153 policewomen.

The study found that the workload experienced by these policewomen is moderate across unit, job, and task levels. Importantly, the study revealed that demographic factors, such as education, length of service, assignment, designation, and training, do not significantly influence either the perception of workload or the actual workload experienced. The most significant challenge encountered by policewomen is the random distribution of unplanned workloads, which can negatively impact job performance.

PNP Health Service has a moderate workload, the lack of influence from demographics suggested a relatively equitable distribution of work. However, the challenges posed by unplanned workloads highlight the need for improved workload management strategies to support policewomen's well-being and performance.

➤ *Conclusion*

In conclusion, this study revealed a moderate workload experienced by female police officers in the PNP Health Service, particularly those who are also mothers. While the distribution of workload appears equitable across different demographic groups, the study highlighted a significant challenge, the random distribution of unplanned workloads. This unpredictable factor negatively impacted job performance and contributes to stress and potential burnout.

The findings suggested that while the PNP Health Service implemented strategies to ensure a fair distribution of work, further improvements in workload management are necessary to support policewomen's well-being and optimize their performance. Addressing unplanned workloads through better planning, communication, and flexibility could significantly enhance the work environment and contribute to a more sustainable and fulfilling career path for policewomen within the PNP Health Service.

➤ *Recommendations*

Intervention program: “Seminar/Workshop on Mental - Health Awareness and Counselling. Proposal for MHA and Counselling as part of institutionalized programs for Women in Police Service (WPS) in the Philippine National Police Health Service.

Personnel orientation/mainstreaming brings about adequate information on the capabilities and limitations of each personnel based on their education, training and expertise. Institutionalizing mainstreaming in every department can help proper allocation of man power based on personal skills and capabilities thus results to the efficiency of services to authorized beneficiaries and all stakeholders. This can also help maximize labor without detaining every personnel from heavy workloads.

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